

SZ-100

Measurement Results

Date : 14 June 2025 14:11:02
Measurement Type : Particle Size
Sample Name : A5
Scattering Angle : 90
Temperature of the Holder : 25.0 °C
Dispersion Medium Viscosity : 2.078 mPa·s
Transmission Intensity before Meas. : 25351
Distribution Form : Standard
Distribution Form(Dispersity) : Monodisperse
Representation of Result : Scattering Light Intensity
Count Rate : 163 kCPS

Calculation Results

Peak No.	S.P.Area Ratio	Mean	S. D.	Mode
1	1.00	751 nm	34 nm	66 nm
2	---	--- nm	--- nm	--- nm
3	---	--- nm	--- nm	--- nm
Total	1.00	751 nm	34 nm	66 nm

Cumulant Operations

Z-Average : 767 nm
PI : 0.523

